

**LAYING THE GROUNDWORK: COMMUNITY CONTRIBUTIONS TO
ECOSYSTEM REGENERATION AND BUSINESS MODEL EMERGENCE**

A Case Study of Regenerative Ocean Farming in Finland

Executive Summary

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EXECUTIVE SUMMARY

Keywords: Regeneration, Community Engagement, Local Ecological Knowledge, Regenerative Business Models, Regenerative Ocean Farming, Ecosystem Regeneration

Nature regeneration is a critical response to biodiversity loss and ecosystem degradation. Regenerative Ocean Farming offers a novel approach combining food production and ecosystem regeneration. However, the foundational role of community actor contributions in enabling ecosystem regenerative practices remains underexplored. This thesis examines the contributions of community actors in early-stage ecosystem regenerative practices and how these contributions lay the foundation for regenerative business model emergence. A qualitative case study was conducted on a community-driven regenerative ocean farming initiative in Finland, focusing on experimental activities on the duck mussel species. Data was collected through seven semi-structured interviews, two field observations, supplemented by virtual meetings and discussions. Findings of this study revealed strategic community roles in early-stage regenerative practices, formation of Strategic Local Ecological Knowledge (Strategic-LEK), and the use of gastronomy as a tool for market and cultural legitimation. These contributions collectively enable conditions for ecosystem regeneration and support the co-emergence of regenerative businesses rooted in place-based ecological knowledge, social collaboration, and cultural values.

ABBREVIATIONS

LEK	Local Ecological Knowledge
TEK	Traditional Ecological Knowledge
IEK	Indigenous Ecological Knowledge
SES	Social-Ecological Systems
LAG	Local Action Group
FLAG	Fisheries Local Action Group
ERC	Ecosystem Restoration Communities
NDC	Neighbourhood Development Centre
MSP	Maritime Spatial Planning
ESM	Earth System Models
LK	Local Knowledge
LTEM	Low-Trophic Extractive Mariculture

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1. PROBLEM DEFINITION

1.1. Ecosystems regeneration and business

Ecosystem Regeneration is a co-evolutionary process where human and business activities contribute to restoring and enhancing social-ecological systems (SES) by adapting to their feedback loops, adaptive rhythms, and place-based needs (Hahn and Tampe, 2021). Sustainable businesses aim to do less harm to the planet, while regenerative businesses go beyond merely being sustainable by enabling the conditions for improving the health and vitality of the planet and people in a simultaneous and synergetic manner (Hahn and Tampe, 2021; Radjou, 2024).

1.2. Regenerative Ocean Farming

Regenerative Ocean Farming,” an emerging approach where aquatic food production is combined with active regeneration of the ocean (Ellen MacArthur, Foundation, 2021). Regenerative ocean farming aims to clean the water, capture carbon, and enhance biodiversity while producing food to actively restore the degraded ocean ecosystem (Cool Blue Future, 2024).

This thesis studies the Regenerative Ocean Farming initiative in the Coastal Ostrobothnia Region in Finland, which is in its formative phase (2024-2025), and is also a part of the Cool Blue (Horizon) and Cool Blue Baltic (EMFAF) projects (Cool Blue Future, 2024). This initiative is primarily driven by the members of Aktion Österbotten, a Local Action Group (LAG) and Fisheries Local Action Group (FLAG) (Aktion Österbotten, 2024), to explore how aquatic food production can be combined with ocean regeneration in Finland. Thus, this research discusses the contribution of community actors to the emergence of early-stage ecosystem regenerative practices and regenerative business models.

1.3. Research gap

There is limited empirical research to understand the community contributions to ecosystem regenerative practices and how they impact the emergence of regenerative businesses. Existing literature often overlooks the important work done by communities to lay the foundation for regenerative practices and the emergence of regenerative business models. There is limited research on how community contribution in these formative stages creates the necessary conditions for ecosystem regeneration and regenerative business models.

The research question of this study was formulated to address this problem, as stated below.

RQ - How do community actors contribute to early-stage ecosystem regenerative practices, and how do their contributions lay the foundations for the emergence of regenerative business models?

In addition to the theoretical contributions, this study offers practical value for individuals involved in early regenerative practices by highlighting their significant contributions in the early development stages before there are any formal ecological or business outcomes.

1.4. Conceptual lens

The lens comprises two core pillars: Community Actor Roles and the formation of Local Ecological Knowledge (LEK).

Figure 4. Conceptual Lens of the Study (Author Generated)

1.5. Research method

The research method of this study is a qualitative, exploratory single case study design to understand how community actors contribute to early-stage regenerative practices and lay the foundation for the emergence of regenerative business models.

Semi-structured interviews and field observations were used as primary data collection methods. The Gioia method (Gioia et al., 2013) was used for data analysis in order to create the empirical model grounded in empirical insights.

Case description. The case study focuses on community-driven regenerative ocean farming initiated in the coastal region of Ostrobothnia in Finland. This initiative aims to explore how food can be produced in the ocean in a regenerative manner, focusing on different species. This study exclusively focuses on the extension of a mussel species named the Duck Mussels (*Anodonta Anatina*). Duck Mussel is a freshwater species that has never been included as a food before.

The goal is to extend the duck mussels in low salinity water of Ostrobothnia with two main targets: to reduce the amount of nutrients of the water solving algae blooms in the coastal areas, and as a mussel

species that is a healthy protein source which can be used by local communities as new locally sourced food. This potentially lays the foundations for the emergence of new regenerative business models.

These efforts began two years ago, initiated by a core team of actors from Aktion Österbotten, a Local Action Group (LAG) and Fisheries Local Action Group (FLAG) that spans across 13 municipalities in Ostrobothnia (Aktion Österbotten, 2024). This project is in an early development phase where initial experimentations, ecological knowledge formation, and exploration of novel food systems are done by several local community actors.

Duck mussel regenerative ocean farming in Ostrobothnia is currently non-commercial as it is not yet commercialized or even extended as a main practice. But the goal of the key actors of this project is to engage local communities with a goal of commercialization in the future. The project has two circles of actors that belong to the local communities. First, it is mainly driven by the key actors and experts of Aktion Österbotten in collaboration with other community actors such as local chefs, fishermen, and researchers. Second, they aim to extend and implement local community engagement this spring and summer season to engage and co-create solutions with land and water owners. As of now, duck mussels are not legalized as a novel food, but pilot and experimental activities are being carried out to generate Local Ecological Knowledge (LEK), raise community awareness, and explore potential future value chains. These community actors contribute at various levels, spanning from initiation and designing the regenerative vision to experimenting and promoting these activities.

Table 6. Summary of Case Study Context

Element	Description
Case Study Title	Community Driven Regenerative Ocean Farming
Geographical Scope	Coastal Region of Ostrobothnia, Finland
Ecosystem	Marine and coastal ecosystems of Ostrobothnia Coastal Region
Regenerative Practice	Ocean Regeneration through different species and explore sustainable food systems
Focus Species of this Study	Duck Mussels (<i>Anodonta anatina</i>)
Development Stage	Early Stage, Exploratory, Pre-commercial
Community Actors	First Circle: Members of Aktion Österbotten, Local Chef, Fishermen, and Researchers Second Circle: Land and Water Owners, Activists and Local Community Members

Table 7. Summary of the Data Collected

Data Type	Participant(s)	Date	Location/Mode
Meeting	3 Members of Aktion Österbotten	11.11.2024	Microsoft Teams
Meeting	3 Members of Aktion Österbotten	18.11.2024	Microsoft Teams
Interview 1	Fisheries Leader Advisor of Aktion Österbotten	25.11.2024	Microsoft Teams
Meeting	3 Members of Aktion Österbotten	16.12.2024	Microsoft Teams
4 hours Workshop (Observation)	3 Members of Aktion Österbotten	16.1.2025	Aktion Österbotten Office
Tasting Event (Observation)	Organized by members Aktion Österbotten. 20 participants: researchers, chef, journalists, fishermen, aquaculture entrepreneurs	16.1.2025	Local Restaurant
Field Work Meeting (Discussion)	Executive Director of Aktion Österbotten	17.1.2025	Personal Setting (in-person)
Interview 2	Biologist Researcher	10.2.2025	Microsoft Teams
Interview 3	Project Manager of Aktion Österbotten	17.2.2025	Microsoft Teams
Interview 4	Fisheries Leader Advisor of Aktion Österbotten	26.2.2025	Microsoft Teams
Interview 5	Owner and chef of the Local Restaurant	4.3.2025	Microsoft Teams
Interview 6	Fishermen A	4.3.2025	Microsoft Teams
Interview 7	Fishermen B	10.3.2025	Microsoft Teams

Table 8. Overview of Interview Participants

Participant Role	Community Context	Sampling Method
Executive Director	Member of Aktion Österbotten	Purposeful
Fisheries Leader Advisor	Member of Aktion Österbotten	Purposeful
Project Manager	Member of Aktion Österbotten	Purposeful
Biologist Researcher	External Academic Collaborator	Snowball
Local Chef	Local Restaurant	Snowball
Fisherman A	Local Community	Snowball
Fisherman B	Local Community	Snowball

Data structure based on qualitative codification

Gioia Data Structure Visual (Author Generated)

Cross-cutting themes

Figure 9. Cross-Cutting Theme of Barriers, Tensions, and Structural Limitations (Author Generated)

2. PROCESS MODEL OF COMMUNITY ENGAGEMENT IN REGENERATIVE OCEAN FARMING

The findings include four dimensions that lay the foundation for building a process model of community engagement in regenerative ocean farming. This process model illustrates that community actors are not merely engaged in predefined roles, but rather strategically initiate, create LEK, foster community engagement, and shape future business approaches to collectively support ecosystem regenerative practices.

Figure 10. Process Model of Community Engagement in Regenerative Ocean Farming Derived Through the Gioia Analysis (Author Generated)

This section is structured around five key interpretations that cut across the four main components of the models, offering a deeper understanding of the dynamics observed in the case.

Figure 11. Key Interpretations Discussed in this Chapter (Author Generated)

2.1. Community Actor Roles in Early-Stage Ecosystem Regenerative Practices

The researcher identified different community roles that contribute to ecosystem regenerative practices. These roles were derived through the synthesis of the literature on community involvement in nature regeneration.

These roles include:

- knowledge holders, such as local and Indigenous communities
- initiators who set the vision and implement initial actions
- collaboration and co-management where communities get together and manage together
- hands-on contributors who participate in active regenerative practices
- monitors and stewards who track the impact with long-term responsibility
- public advocates who contribute in raising awareness and policy changes

Initiators. Initiator can be defined as individuals or an organization that takes the first strategic steps in launching these ecosystem regenerative practices. This role extends beyond facilitating participation or implementing technical work. Initiators create and are responsible for establishing the foundational structure, designing the vision and goals, securing funding and resources, and actively collaborating with external community members to involve them in the initiative. In simple words, initiators are the foundational pillars who transform a regenerative idea into an actionable reality. In this study, the initiators were the three key individuals from Aktion Österbotten: the Executive Director, the Fisheries Leader Advisor, and the Project Manager.

The findings reveal how initiators think long-term, to find solutions to ecological degradation by engaging in novel activities. Their vision is to produce food in a regenerative way so that it also cleans the water, regenerating the ocean. Initiators are visionaries and system designers whose tasks go beyond simple operational work, where they move the regenerative vision and logic forward even if there is no formal roadmap to follow, which is clear in this case study.

Early stage collaborators include a local chef, fishermen, and a biologist researcher were included in the initial phases for knowledge, experimentation, and engagement activities. They bring support, enthusiasm, place-based knowledge, and credibility to the initiative implemented by the initiators. Therefore, their role is not passive but rather enabled by the strategic foundation laid by the initiators.

External community actors. Further, it was evident that initiators collaborate to bring together external community actors into the process. Other community actor roles the researcher identified in the

literature synthesis, such as knowledge holders, monitors, stewards, and policy reformers, were not yet fully present due to the early-stage phase of this case.

Process. Initiator was identified as a foundational community actor role in early-stage ecosystem regenerative practices. Along with them, early-stage collaborators also play an important supporting role. Identifying these different key community roles is important to understand that regenerative initiatives are not spontaneous or widely community-driven from the beginning, but rather carefully initiated and structured through the strategic community contributions of a few actors.

2.2. Strategic Local Ecological Knowledge Formation

The formation of LEK was strongly observed in this case study. In the initiation itself, community actors recognized the need to build ecological knowledge from the ground up because of the novelty of using duck mussels, a freshwater species, to regenerate the ocean while producing food. Findings demonstrate that the knowledge was not inherently present from lived experiences and livelihoods as described in the literature (Charnley et al., 2007, Davis and Wagner, 2003). Thus, initiators began to create strategic and project-driven LEK with the support of early-stage collaborators, which literature reflects as LEK formation through collaborations between different stakeholders (Albareda and Branzei, 2024; Emard et al., 2024; Ruddle and Davis, 2011).

LEK was not gradually accumulated but rather formed in a more rapid, targeted phase to achieve specific goals. While the literature notes that LEK can be adaptive (Joa et al., 2018; Leithäuser and Holzhaacker, 2020), the empirical findings demonstrate a proactive and more organized approach to LEK creation as a result of the regenerative initiative. They performed various structured experiments, collaborative learning, and iterative engagement activities to build the knowledge needed. This aligns with the understanding that LEK is formed through observations, experiences, and trial and error (Charnley et al., 2007; Hilary and Martin, 1999).

However, the difference in the case study is that this knowledge is being generated purposefully to achieve ecological and economic goals through experimentation, observations, and trial-and-error. Therefore, this can be named as “Strategic Local Ecological Knowledge (Strategic-LEK)” formation.

LEK was not passively inherited in this case but co-created, purposefully combining scientific and hands-on local experimentation with forward-looking processes, which illustrates the early-stage development of this ecosystem regenerative practice.

Moreover, in this case, knowledge was not only about scientific discovery, but it was a mix of a deep local, cultural, sensory, culinary, and scientific process (Emard et al., 2024; Joa et al., 2018; Ruddle and Davis, 2011; Toner et al., 2023).

In this case, strategic-LEK emerged as the invisible infrastructure of early-stage regenerative practices, which was a co-produced, experimented, and deeply contextual knowledge that enables the future emergence of regenerative entrepreneurship and business models (Rahman et al., 2024).

2.3. Motivational Drivers in Early-Stage Community Engagement

The findings from the case study reveal that community engagement is focused and limited. This reflects the early-stage nature of the initiative, where engagement is strategically cultivated rather than spontaneously spread.

Engagement at this stage is primarily handled by initiators and a few early-stage collaborators, by engaging in experiments, trials, and laying the foundation for broader public involvement. The findings reflect that initiators are focusing on building credibility, clarifying the vision and goals, and building LEK before involving communities at a large scale. Their contributions in this early stage indicate a strategic and deliberate approach for building the conditions needed before broader inclusion.

The main motivational driver that pushed initiators to engage in this regenerative practice was the foundational vision of “producing food in a way that cleans the water.” This primary vision was the initial motivator for initiators, which was then combined with the immediate driver of needing to collaboratively build LEK, which drove the engagement of early-stage collaborators.

Vision and mission. The findings suggest that community engagement is driven by the exciting “why” (the regenerative vision), and the curious “how” (the need for building LEK) as the foundational, shared driver for initial participation. Therefore, it can be suggested that a compelling vision, when clearly communicated, can drive the interest of community engagement, which draws curious community actors, problem-solvers, nature-lovers, and explorers interested in trying new things.

Novelty. Another significant motivational driver expressed in the findings was the role of novelty, which lays the foundation for pioneering and being an ambassador, which emerges in this early stage. The opportunity to be involved in something new and untested drew the interest of the local chef and fishermen B.

Biophilia. Empirical findings suggest that this sense of ownership is enhanced by emotional and cultural attachments such as love for the sea, desire to keep the harbor alive, and concerns about algae blooms. This shows that motivation for participation is also driven by the love for their surrounding nature (Albareda and Branzei, 2024; González-Torres et al., 2024; Sinclair et al., 2024).

2.4. Gastronomy as Legitimation in Regenerative Engagement

Findings demonstrate that mussels are culturally not known in the Finnish culinary culture, therefore, tasting events hosted supported introducing duck mussels through taste and sensory experience. The local chef experimented with the duck mussels as well as planned for further testing to create delicious

dishes supporting culinary legitimacy. As of this stage, duck mussels cannot be commercialized; therefore, tasting events offered direct exposure to the product. The literature explains the role of collaborations with community actors for ecosystem regeneration practices (eg, Asaduzzaman et al., 2024; Lähde et al., 2024; Montenegro et al., 2024), and in this case, chefs function as cultural translators by transforming this novel species into an exploratory dish for the public. In addition, these culinary experimentations are a method of LEK formation.

Discursive grounding. The findings suggest that gastronomic storytelling that aligns with local identity and environmental values supports building trust in this regenerative practice. The local chef framed duck mussels as a local innovation that is a locally sourced, healthy, and sustainable protein. The literature review explains that the emotional and cultural connection to a place could be a driver for engagement (Albareda and Branzei, 2024; Sinclair et al., 2024; González-Torres et al., 2024). Therefore, it can be suggested that in this case, gastronomy acts as an emotional and cultural factor allowing the engagement of community members in this novel practice.

Although there are no commercial activities yet, the gastronomic success of duck mussels plays a huge role in ecological, cultural, and market legitimacy. As mentioned before, this is not a known food in Finland; therefore, tasting events increase community awareness and create a demand.

Process. In conclusion, the findings reveal that community actors, especially in this case, chefs, contribute to early-stage regenerative practices by embedding novelties in cultural context and transforming them into tangible, trusted, and sensory experiences.

2.5. Laying the Groundwork for Regenerative Business Models

It is evident that a formal regenerative business model for duck mussels is not yet in operation, however, the findings reveal the presence of an early-stage business logic mindset and imaginaries that lay the foundation for future regenerative business model emergence.

Findings show that the end goal of this initiative is to establish a regenerative business model in the future that includes ecological, social, and economic benefits.

No formal regenerative business model. Although there is no formal business model yet in this case, there is an alignment with the core principles and characteristics of regenerative business models as described in the literature review. Literature highlights that regenerative business models co-evolve and co-create with nature, understanding that it is one system and cannot operate in isolation, and is embedded in a SES (Hahn and Tampe, 2021; Konietzko et al., 2023). Community actors in this case understand that humans are interdependent on natural systems, which was one of the major reasons behind the initiation of this project. Further, initiators involved various community actors for early-stage development activities, aligning with the multistakeholder value creation characteristic described in the literature by creating and delivering value at multiple stakeholder levels through collaborations

(Das and Bocken, 2024; Konietzko et al., 2023). In addition, the literature review emphasizes that regenerative business focuses on addressing place-based needs by focusing on unique ecological and social requirements of the local environment (Slawinski et al., 2019).

Process. It can be suggested that regenerative business models in the community context initiate from a foundation of cultural values and commitment to nature regeneration, which is driven by LEK formation (Albareda and Branzei, 2024). In Finland, the initiative was started with a vision to produce food while cleaning the water, which led to hands-on trial activities and collaborative engagement for LEK formation. As discussed before, this was primarily driven by community motivations and connections to nature before any business or economic incentives become a driver.

Figure 12. Empirical Model Developed to Answer the Research Question of the Study (Author Generated)

3. RECOMMENDATIONS

This study offers several practical implications for individuals involved in initiating, designing, supporting, and participating in early-stage regenerative practices.

The co-creation of community-driven vision. First, the findings highlight the importance of the co-creation of community-driven vision as the foundation for ecosystem regenerative practices. Practitioners and policymakers should understand the important role played by initiators in laying the foundation, building the structure, engaging external stakeholders, and establishing a shared vision before formal business approaches begin. Thus, it is crucial to recognize and support these roles through funding, facilitation, and long-term trust to strengthen these regenerative efforts.

Legitimation of consumption and engagement practices. A new implication identified was the role of gastronomy as a legitimizing and engagement tool. Sensory engagement and storytelling are important in early-stage regeneration in order to familiarise the public with unfamiliar products and create awareness. Therefore, approaches related to chefs, restaurants, public events, and culinary experiences should be given importance as a part of the regenerative strategy, especially when it involves novel food-based practices.

Local ecological and place-based knowledge and infrastructure. This study underpins the importance of supporting the invisible and emergent work that is done before formal structures or certifications exist, which results in more locally rooted, culturally aligned, and ecologically regenerative business models.

Vision and mission built by initiators. Further, the early-stage collaborators identified in this study are not simply side players but rather key partners engaging in activities to make this vision a reality. Finally, this thesis brings value to the initiators of this regenerative journey in Ostrobothnia. Their courage and interest to begin without a clear roadmap, engage external stakeholders, and envision a future where nature regeneration, business, and entrepreneurship are interconnected showcase their innovation and care for nature, which should be recognized and supported. Initiators and early-stage collaborators go beyond simply being participants; they co-create knowledge and engage in experimentation, working towards a shared vision with a deep commitment to place, people, and the planet. This research captures only a small part of their ongoing work and encourages future practitioners, institutions, and funders to recognize and support such initiatives as the basic building blocks of ecosystem regeneration.

4. REGENERATIVE PRACTICES

In this study, regenerative practice is in its early development stage. The tables bring the set of practices identified that can be applied to further develop the project.

First-Order Concepts	Second-Order Themes	Aggregated Dimensions
<p>Fisheries Leader Advisor's Personal Vision for Mussel Farming</p> <p>Fisheries Leader Advisor Recognized Project Manager's Skills in Innovation</p> <p>Fisheries Leader Advisor Wanted to Recruit Project Manager Earlier</p> <p>Change in the Industry Always Starts with a Few Pioneers</p> <p>Change in the Fishing Industry Always Starts with a Few Pioneers</p> <p>First Few People Should Get Involved and Start to Build Demand</p> <p>Key Person or Persons Need to Start Something New to Drive Others</p> <p>Roles of Leaders and Models Depend on the Location and Community</p> <p>Project Leadership and Responsibilities</p> <p>Need for a Strategic Approach</p> <p>Success of Mussel Farming Depends on Key Individuals in the Community</p> <p>Goal Is to Develop Duck Mussel Farming</p> <p>Goal to Develop Duck Mussel Production Systems</p> <p>Identifying Candidate Species for Regenerative Ocean Farming in Finland</p> <p>Long-Term Goal Is Developing a Production Model for Duck Mussels</p> <p>Identifying Regenerative Ocean Farming Possibilities in Finland</p>	<p>Strategic Visioning and Leadership</p>	<p>Strategic Foundations for Regenerative Practice</p>
<p>Building a Proper Network</p> <p>Connection to the Project Through Existing Networks</p> <p>Good Collaboration with Facilitators</p> <p>Long-Term Collaboration with Fisheries Advisor</p> <p>Managing Multiple Related Projects</p> <p>Need for a Collaborative Network</p> <p>Relationship with Fisheries Advisor Through Fisheries and Network</p> <p>Project Partners Across Multiple Countries</p> <p>Chef as an Ambassador for Finnish Cuisine</p> <p>The Fisherman Considers Himself a Pioneer in Innovation</p> <p>Acting as an Ambassador for the Project</p> <p>Working with International Partners</p> <p>Organization Location</p> <p>Purpose of Cool Blue Platform</p>	<p>Network and Collaborative Efforts</p>	

<p>The Cool Blue Project and Cool Baltic Project Other Projects Organisation Engaged With European Union's Role in Ecosystem Restoration Exploring Funding Opportunities Collaboratively Hiring Someone for Further Investigation</p>	
<p>Need to Increase Duck Mussel Production Aktion Österbotten Goal Is Food Production Now Trying to Understand How to Grow from That First Reproduction Stage Fishermen Are Important for Testing, Not Production As a Fisherman, Mussels Farming Is Not a Challenge Role in the Mussel Project Planning for Spring and Summer Activities Hatchery Development Is Key for Scaling Mussel Farming Hatchery at the University for Pearl Mussels Not Just Waiting for Lab-Based Hatchery Exploring Natural Hatchery Locations Trying to Develop a New Hatchery Method Without Fish</p>	<p>Production Infrastructure and Strategic Planning</p>
<p>Project Is Still in Testing Phase Still in the Early Stages of Testing the Idea Developing Mussel Cages for Farming Site Selection for Mussel Farming Requires Consideration of Other Interests Site Selection for Mussel Placement – Depth, Protection, and Currents Finding Best Locations for Community Mussel Placement Choosing Locations for Community-Based Mussel Farming Requires Planning Coastal Waters Could Be Used for Rearing Mussels Before Commercial Production Controlled Placement of Mussels to Improve Survival Potential Hatchery Locations Floating Island Concept for Mussel Farming Potential for Controlled Farming Using Bags or Containers Importance of Quantitative Data to Show People the Results Need to Get Real Reports on How to Grow Mussels</p>	<p>Testing, Site Selection, and Experimental Foundations</p>

<p>Need for a Proof of Concept and Clear Guidelines for Fishermen Participation Applying for a Larger Research Project With a University Applying for Funding to Support Research Potential for Funding in Regenerative Projects</p>		
<p>Duck Mussels Grow Quite Fast Compared to Other Mussels Mussel Growth Is Very Slow Duck Mussels Already Exist in Nature Salinity Affect on Mussel Growth Influence of Salinity on Mussels Mussels Enter Dormancy in Cold Temperatures Negative Environmental Factors Affecting Mussels Negative Effects of Acidification on Mussels Confirmation That Ecosystems Have a Mussel Limit All Mussel Species Play a Similar Role in Ecosystems Mussel Quality Based on Environment High Filtration Capacity of Duck Mussels Distinguishing Between Duck Mussels & Swan Mussels Duck and Swan Mussels as Best Options Human Activities and Mussel Population Decline High Natural Mussel Populations in Some Lakes Natural Spread of Duck Mussels Reproduction and Life Cycle of Duck Mussels Complexity of Duck Mussel Reproduction Understanding Mussel Reproduction Cycle Growth Cycle of Duck Mussels Method to Count the Age of a Mussel Feeding and Growth of Juvenile Mussels Mussels' Adaptation to Environmental Conditions Mussels' Response to Pollution and Oxygen Levels Fish Farms and Hatcheries as Solutions for Growing Mussels Potential for Regenerative Ocean Farming Beyond Duck Mussels Alternative to Hatchery by Putting Mussels from Nature to Coastal Areas</p>	<p>Building Biological and Reproductive Knowledge of Duck Mussels</p>	<p>Local Ecological Knowledge Formation</p>

<p>Can Use Alternative Mussel Species for Regeneration Finding Best Areas in Finland for Growing Dark Mussels Finding Best Conditions for Mussels Intended for Consumption Suitability of Finnish Coastal Waters for Mussels Finland Has Potential for Regenerative Ocean Farming Despite Challenges Status of Dark Mussels in Finland vs. Europe Low Salinity in Finnish Waters Aquaculture Is Emerging in Finland Source of Mother Mussels for Reproduction Alternative Mussel Species Can Be Used for Regeneration</p>	
<p>Mussel Beds as Biodiversity Hotspots Mussel Shells Providing Habitat for Other Species Mussels Mixing Sediment and Enhancing Oxygen Levels Mussels Reducing Harmful Bacteria in Water Mussels' Role in Removing Fish Pathogens Mussels Reducing Fish Parasites Nutrient Removal from Water Ecosystems Sediment Modification and Water Quality Improvement of Duck Mussels Mussels in Lake and River Restoration Projects Duck Mussel Farming Is Equally Interesting for Food and Water Regeneration Combining Mussels & Floating Gardens for Pollution Control Using Mussels in Fish Farms to Support Fish Health Potential Health Benefits for Fish from Being Near Mussels Applications of Duck Mussel Farming Alternative Uses for Duck Mussels Beyond Food Using Mussels in Graveyard Monitoring Water Cleaning Effectiveness Hatchery vs. Wild Mussels' Filtration Efficiency Growth Timeline for Water Cleaning Use</p>	<p>Building Environmental and Ecosystem Services Knowledge of Duck Mussels</p>
<p>Duck Mussels Have a Muddy Taste When Taken from the Bottom</p>	<p>Building Sensory and Culinary</p>

<p>Change in Mussel Flavor Based on Environment Location Impacts Mussel Taste, Open Waters Produce Better Flavor Mussels Must Be Lifted from the Mud for Good Taste Mussels Absorb the Flavor of Their Environment Mussels Accumulating Heavy Metals So Not Edible Surface Placement of Mussels May Cause Damage Mussels Survive After Being Moved Sterile Environments Reduce Mussel Flavor Optimal Environmental Conditions for Filtration Put In Sea, Tastes Like Ocean</p>	<p>Knowledge of Duck Mussels</p>
<p>Continual Learning & Problem Solver Regular Meetings to Share Knowledge Collaboration with Other Experts on Water Cleaning Research on Duck Mussel Reproduction by University Learning About Duck Mussel Biology from the Seminar Fish Farmers Assisted in Relocation of Mussels Fisherman Has Helped with Experimenting Collaboration with Different Stakeholders Like Aquaculture, Fishermen, and Youth Projects Fisherman's Role in the Experiment: Transporting, Equipment, and Deploying Mussels Following the Project and Open to Helping in Future Testing How Mussels Should Be Handed to Communities from Specialists Introduction to Duck Mussels Through the Project People Accidentally Finding Mussels While Swimming Introducing Dark Mussels to a New Coastal Area First Thing Was Testing Different Cage Models for Duck Mussels Experimenting with New Cage Designs for Next Season Testing & Deploying Mussel Cages in Spring</p>	<p>Collaborative Experimentations and Knowledge Co-creation</p>

<p>Testing Natural Growth & Survival of Mussels</p> <p>Testing Different Depths for Mussel Growth</p> <p>Is the Plan for 2025</p> <p>Find a Method to Get the Mussels as Fast as Possible</p> <p>Test to Create Natural Hatchery</p> <p>Using Nature to Accelerate the Hatchery Process</p> <p>More Effective Alternative to Lab Hatcheries</p> <p>Lantern Net Model Proves Most Effective Size & Structure of Mussel Cages</p> <p>Exploring Alternative Uses for Duck Mussels</p> <p>Testing Nutrient Content & Applications of Duck Mussels</p> <p>Importance of Studying Nutritional Content and Health Benefits</p> <p>Investigating Mussel Taste & Quality</p> <p>Lab Testing and Researching Duck Mussels</p> <p>One Year of Testing Needed for Initial Results</p> <p>Using a Secchi Disk to Measure Water Clarity</p> <p>Combining Natural & Semi-Laboratory Methods</p>		
<p>Finnish Connection to the Sea</p> <p>Community Awareness & Interest in Regenerative Practices</p> <p>Community Interest in the Environment</p> <p>Interest in Healthier, More Sustainable Food Production</p> <p>Interest in Regenerative Thinking</p> <p>Local Memory and Motivation for Restoration</p> <p>Community Engagement in Environmental Restoration</p> <p>Potential Positive Environmental Impact of Mussel Farming</p> <p>Mussels Enhance Ecosystem Balance & Function</p> <p>Public Concern About Algae Blooms in Lakes</p> <p>Preventing Algae Blooms Using Mussels & Gardens</p> <p>Improving Biodiversity and Getting Food at the Same Time</p> <p>Interest from Local Fish Farmers</p> <p>Farmers & Municipalities Might Participate for Environmental Reasons</p>	<p>Emotional, Cultural, and Environmental Drivers for Engagement</p>	<p>Motivations, Mechanisms, and Pathways for Community Engagement</p>

<p>Good PR for Fish Farmers to Reverse Their Environmental Damage Willingness to Innovate to Stay Competitive</p>	
<p>Excitement Around Pioneering a New Industry People Are Curious About Farming Duck Mussels Interest in Producing Food in a Regenerative Way Commitment to Local Ingredients Interest in New Challenges Curiosity About New Species That Can Survive in Low-Salinity Waters Interest in Trying Duck Mussels Interest in Trying New Things Interested and Not Afraid To Try New Things Growing Interest in Duck Mussel Interest of Fishers and Farmers in Duck Mussels Losing Previous Job & Transitioning to Regenerative Work Restaurants May Be Interested for Branding and Storytelling People Liked the Taste of Duck Mussels The Mussel Tasting Event Was Inspirational Role of Public Interest in Determining Future Directions Increasing Consumer Awareness of Sustainability Some Enthusiasts May Be Interested</p>	<p>Curiosity, Novelty, and Excitement as a Local Product</p>
<p>Economic Incentives as a Motivator to Grow Mussels Fisherman Will Be Interested if They Know That Mussels Will Be an Extra Income Fishermen Would Be Interested if It Adds Value to Their Business Participation Depends on Profit Main Interest in Expanding Product Portfolio Beyond Fish Regenerative Ocean Farming as More of a Commercial Thing Than a Community Thing Motivation as Balancing Practical Work & Research Limited Involvement from Other Fishermen So Far Different Motivations for Community Involvement Can't Force Communities to Engage</p>	<p>Economic, Feasibility, and New Business Opportunity</p>

<p>Participation in International Seminar on Ocean Regeneration</p>		
<p>Getting the Message to Public Future Media Engagement on Duck Mussels Local Newspaper Coverage National Media Coverage Media Interest in Mussel Project Openness to Publicity and Awareness Efforts Sharing Success Stories to Gain Public Support Spreading the Word Is Important Participating in Public Events Stakeholder Engagement Through Site Visits and Media Organizing Public Demonstrations and Educational Initiatives Plan to Create a Centralized Demonstration Site Practical Demonstrations of the Process Creating an Aquarium to Show Mussels to the Public Inviting Media to Tasting Event Raising Awareness of Duck Mussels Need for Scientific Information to Convince the Public to Eat Mussels Need for Training & Education for Community Involvement Need More Knowledge to Get More Involved Start Engaging Communities with Basic Guidelines, Purpose, and Information Training Needed for Communities on How to Handle Baby Mussels Before Releasing Them Organized Help on How to Get Mussels for Farming How Mussels Should Be Handed to Communities from Specialists Communities Can Just Put the Mussels in Water, No Take Care Needed Using Children as a Pathway to Community Engagement Local Community Members Are Better Suited for Farming Community-Based Models Could Be Revived Engaging More People to Participate Have Different Ways of Motivating and Engaging Communities</p>	<p>Public Outreach, Awareness, Education, and Sensory Engagement Strategies</p>	
<p>Duck Mussels as a Locally Sourced Seafood</p>	<p>Gastronomic Framing and</p>	<p>Pathways for the Emergence of</p>

	Cultural Narrative Building	Regenerative Business Models
<p>Duck Mussels for Environmental and Culinary Use</p> <p>Mussels as Food</p> <p>Mussels Are an Environmentally Friendly Protein Source</p> <p>Mussels as an Easy-to-Cook Ingredient</p> <p>Mussels can be used in Different Ways</p> <p>Potential for Different Cooking Methods for Duck Mussels</p> <p>Nutritional Benefits of Mussels</p> <p>Taste of Duck Mussels</p> <p>Texture and Cooking Comparison to Other Shell Food</p> <p>Flavour of the Mussel Matters More than the Texture</p> <p>Importance of Mussel Size for Cooking</p> <p>Mussel Sausages in Post-War Germany</p> <p>Mussels Having a Neutral Taste</p> <p>Preference for Locally Produced Seasonal Ingredients</p> <p>Duck Mussels as a New Food in Finland</p> <p>Duck Mussels as a Seasonal Product</p> <p>Duck Mussels as a Niche Product with Limited Appeal</p> <p>Comparing Duck Mussels Novelty to Other Foods</p> <p>Comparing Meat to Seafood</p> <p>Shift in Finnish Cuisine Toward Seafood</p> <p>Younger Generations Are More Open to New Foods</p> <p>Guest Reaction to the Mussel Tasting Event</p> <p>Guests Being Excited at the Tasting Event</p> <p>Testing Duck Mussel Taste With Public and Restaurants</p> <p>Chef's First Impression of Duck Mussels</p> <p>Overall Positive Impression of Duck Mussels from Chef</p> <p>Positive Feedback from Chef on Duck Mussel Taste from His Fish Farm</p> <p>Chef's Limited Experience With Shellfish & Interest in Experimenting</p> <p>Restaurants as the Main Market</p> <p>Willingness of Chefs to Work with Mussels</p> <p>If The Price is ok Chefs Will Try It</p> <p>Chefs Are Key to Market Creation and Promotion</p> <p>Chef's Effort in Promoting Finnish Products</p> <p>Role of Chefs and Restaurants in Creating Demand</p> <p>Testing and Introducing to Restaurants</p>		

<p>Why Chef Was Chosen for the Mussel Project Collaboration with Chefs and Restaurants to Build Demand Expectation That Chefs in Finland Will Be Interested Expectation That Mussels Will Reach the Market Quickly Testing Mussels in a Restaurant Possible Need to Modify Cooking Process for Duck Mussels Ensuring Food Safety Through Cooking Optimal Conditions for Mussels Meant for Food</p>		
<p>Possibility of Using Cleaned Mussels for Food Depends on Water Source No Hygiene Concerns About Mussels from Fish Farms No Known Health Risks From Eating Duck Mussels Extra Income with Little Effort with Mussel Farming Mussel Farming Requires Less Daily Work Than Fishing Workload of Mussel Farming Compared to Fishing Ease of Mussel Farming Compared to Fishing Equipment Setup Existing Fishing Infrastructure Can Be Used for Mussel Farming Duck Mussel Farming Needs to Be Economically Viable Long-Term Business Potential of Duck Mussel Farming Duck Mussels as a Protein Source Should Be Cheap Mussels Don't Weigh Much So Will Need a Big Volume for Profit Need to Do Calculations on Pricing Profitability and Market Size for Mussels Will Be the Main Challenge Uncertainty in Texture and Cooking Methods and Need More Experimentation Need to Find How Fast They Grow to Commercialize Investment Requirements for Commercial Mussel Farming Harvesting Efficiency of Mussels If Mussels Can Be Grown Commercial Then Fishermen Will Be Interested</p>	<p>Economic Viability and Requirements Needed for Commercialization</p>	

<p>In Short Term It Is Fun but In Long Term There Needs to Be Profits Potential for Large-Scale Duck Mussel Production Without Environmental Harm Mussel Price Should Be Cheap as a Protein Source Small-Scale Farming Might Start Next Year Scaling Up Mussel Farming Would Require More Cages, Not Larger Ones Scalability and Market Penetration Dependent on Price Factors to Consider for Commercialization Need to Differentiate Mussels Used for Cleaning vs. Those for Food Limited Evidence of Duck Mussels as Food Evidence of Duck Mussel as a Food More Research Needed on Duck Mussels More Research Is Needed Before Commercialization Testing for Pollutants and Nutrient Content in Mussels Positive Lab Test Results Need Further Investigations on Novelty Future of Duck Mussels as a Business Depends on Reproduction Success Uncertainty About Production Cost Uncertainty About Large-Scale Market for Mussels</p>		
<p>Different Business Models Based on Different Interests Community vs. Business-Oriented Mussel Farming Models Need for Hybrid or Alternative Models for Community Mussel Farming Public-Private Partnership or Joint Venture Hatcheries Aligning Mussel Farming with EU Agricultural Subsidies Seeking Larger Project Opportunities Scaling Up & Finding the Right Expertise Potential for Mussels as a Global Protein Solution Potential Use of Mussels in Fish Farming as Compensation Models Potential Connection Between Mussels and Fish Farms Potential Interest from Fish Farming Industry Potential Interest from Other Fishermen in Mussel Farming</p>	<p>Entrepreneurial Imagination and Opportunity Recognition</p>	

<p>Framing Regenerative Aquaculture as a Job Creation Opportunity Discovering Job Opportunity in Regenerative Ocean Farming Interest in Duck Mussel Farming as a New Business Opportunity</p>		
Cross-Cutting Theme		
<p>Unique Challenges of Regenerative Ocean Farming in Finland Budget requirements for hatchery No Environmental Risks Identified Project Is in Early Stages, No Commercial Involvement Yet To Engage Fishermen in Farming Need a Production Model for Duck Mussels Not Many Are Actively Involved Not Important for Community Engagement Fishermen Will Only Participate if Paid Fisherman Are Not the First Target Group for Production Low Demand for Mussels in Finnish Households Mussels Are Not a Traditional Finnish Food Culturally Not Known to Consume Mussels in Finland Duck Mussels Are Not Traditionally Consumed in Europe Finnish Consumers Are Conservative About Eating Mussels Lack of Awareness About Finnish Ingredients Lack of Cultural Habit of Eating Mussels Mussels Are Not a Part of Finnish Food Culture Seafood Is Not Common in Finland Need for Sustainable Cultivation Instead of Wild Harvesting Not Sure of the Risks from Seals and Seabirds for Mussels Agricultural and Forestry Activities Contribute to Nutrient Pollution Aquaculture Is Needed Because Can't Rely on Fish Concern About Overharvesting and Sustainability Concern About the State of the Marine Ecosystem Concerns Over Decreasing Fish Availability Declining Mussel Populations & Habitat Destruction</p>		<p>Barriers, Tensions & Structural Limitations</p>

Duck Mussels Are Not Visible for People
Novel Food Is Not the Main Thing
Anticipated Future Commercialization
Timeline of Duck Mussels
Anyway Can't Sell
Challenges with Authorities and Regulatory
Approval
Current Lack of Specific Legal Framework
for Mussel Farming
EU Funding Important for Fisheries, Not Sure
Whether It's the Same With Mussels
Finland Has Strict Permit Regulations for
Coastal Activities
Frustration with Novel Food Legalization
Process
Funding Challenges and FLAG Project
Involvement
Government Leases Are Required for
Offshore Areas
Importance of Quantitative Data for Funding
Importance of Quantitative Data for Scaling
and Regulation
Is Novel Food Approval Needed
It Will Take at Least Three Years to Write a
Farming Guide
Lack of Clear Farming Guidelines
Legal Rights Were There as a Fisherman
Helped in Site Selection for Initial
Experiment
More Practical Testing Needed Before Wider
Adoption
Need Experts to Investigate Novel Food
Process
Need for Hatchery Funding
Need for Legal Approval Before
Commercialization
Need for Subsidies to Support Early Adoption
of Mussel Farming
No Clear Process for Novel Food Approval
No Limit on Duck Mussels in Fish Farms,
Just Area Restrictions
No Proper Hatchery for Dark Mussels Yet
No Proper Mapping of Mussels
No Special License Needed, Just Water
Permits
Not Farming Yet
Novel Food Approval is Expensive & Time-
Consuming
Novel Food Legalization is a Formality, Not a
Major Issue

Possible Need for Regulatory Action Only if
Complaints Arise
Regulatory Authorities Avoiding the Duck
Mussel Novel Food Topic
So Far Don't Know How the Real
Commercial Duck Mussel Production Would
Look Like or Happen
Uncertain About Commercial Farming
Participation But Have a Positive Attitude
Uncertainty of Getting Novel Food Approval
Uncertainty About Why Mussels Are Not
Eaten
Uncertainty Around Duck Mussel Farming &
Commercial Uses
Uncertainty Around the Novel Food Status of
Duck Mussels
Water Ownership and Permit Requirements
Vary by Location in Finland
Challenges in Achieving Consistent Flavor of
Mussels
Challenges in Early Growth Stages of
Mussels
Challenges in Handling and Securing the
Mussel Cages
Challenges in Raising Dark Mussels in
Controlled Conditions
Challenges of Growing Freshwater Mussels
in Coastal Finland
Challenges of Growing Mussels in
Laboratory Settings
Concerns About Mussels Absorbing
Contaminants
Difficulty in Measuring the Water-Cleaning
Effect of Mussels
Effective Reproduction Is the Main Challenge
Finding Suitable Locations for Mussel
Farming Takes Time
No Noticeable Growth in Two Months
Removal of Mussels Due to Ice Formation
Uncertainty About Mussel Availability
Uncertainty About Optimal Depth for Mussel
Growth So Experimenting This Next Season
Uncertainty About the Worth of Fish
Hatchery Method's Success
Uncertainty of How Exactly Mussels
Handling Is Done
Visual Water Clean Monitoring Challenges
Can Take Mussels from Nature in Some
Cases

<p>Fishing Rights and Their Potential Role in Mussel Farming Getting Mussels from Nature Not a Long-Term Solution Open Waters Are Unsuitable for Community-Based Mussel Farming Possibility of Getting the Novel Food Approval</p>	
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